

Bridging the Language Divide: A Bilingual Conversational AI Chatbot for Pandemic Surveillance in Uganda

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Abstract

Background. Pandemic preparedness in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) is hindered by limited access to complex disease surveillance guidelines, particularly among frontline health workers with suboptimal English proficiency. Uganda's Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response (IDSR) guidelines, while comprehensive, remain largely underutilized due to their length, English-only format, and frequent health worker turnovers. Large language models (LLMs) have demonstrated potential in making medical knowledge more accessible, but their utility for disease surveillance is limited when they rely solely on general medical training data rather than country-specific protocols. Without explicit grounding in local IDSR guidelines, LLMs may provide responses that conflict with Uganda's standardized case definitions, reporting requirements, or outbreak response procedures. Additionally, the dominance of English in AI systems excludes the majority of African health workers who operate primarily in indigenous languages, creating barriers to equitable access to AI-enabled health tools.

Methods: We developed HEAL, a custom bilingual chatbot leveraging GPT-4-turbo and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) to make Uganda's IDSR guidelines conversationally accessible in English and Luganda. We created 59,699 question-answer pairs from the guidelines and trained an MBart model using yy sentence pairs for translation. Six disease surveillance experts from Uganda's Ministry of Health evaluated responses generated using four approaches: HEAL's RAG-grounded system (GPT-4-turbo with IDSR guideline access) and three baseline commercial LLMs (GPT-3.5, GPT-4, and Gemini) without IDSR guideline access. Evaluation used 50 field-generated questions across four metrics: relevance, coverage, coherence, and harm.

Results: Responses generated with retrieval-augmented access to Uganda's IDSR guidelines received significantly higher scores than responses generated from general medical knowledge alone. Three of six reviewers (reviewers 1, 4, and 5) assigned higher median scores to RAG-grounded responses, with highly significant differences observed by reviewers 1 and 5 ($p < 0.001$). RAG-grounded responses significantly outperformed baseline responses in coverage and relevance metrics when evaluated by expert reviewers. These findings demonstrate that grounding LLM responses in local surveillance protocols substantially improves their utility for disease surveillance tasks. Qualitative feedback from frontline health workers and surveillance officers confirmed the practical value of locally contextualized guidance in reducing false alerts and improving resource allocation, though infrastructural challenges (internet connectivity, device availability) were noted as barriers to widespread adoption.

Conclusions: This study demonstrates that retrieval-augmented generation using local IDSR guidelines substantially improves LLM performance for disease surveillance guidance in resource-limited settings. Responses grounded in Uganda's surveillance protocols demonstrated significantly better coverage and relevance compared to baseline responses generated from general medical knowledge alone. By combining RAG-based contextual grounding with English-Luganda translation capabilities, we address both the knowledge gap between general medical information and local surveillance protocols and the linguistic exclusion that prevents many African health workers from accessing AI-enabled tools. Frontline health workers confirmed the system's acceptability and practical utility in real-world surveillance workflows. Our work provides a scalable framework for linguistically inclusive, locally grounded AI in global health. However, technical feasibility alone is insufficient. Realizing AI's potential in LMICs requires sustained investment in low-resource language development, infrastructural solutions to connectivity barriers, and deliberate efforts to ensure AI advancement reduces rather than amplifies health inequities.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Disease Surveillance, Large Language Models, Uganda, Pandemic Preparedness, Linguistic Equity, IDSR, Retrieval-Augmented Generation

BACKGROUND

Pandemics pose existential threats to global health security, with disproportionate impacts on low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) that face structural barriers to effective disease surveillance and response [1]. The fear and anxiety accompanying disease outbreaks create fertile ground for misinformation, delaying case identification and compromising timely treatment. Yet seamless access to quality, verifiable health information remains severely limited in

resource-constrained settings. Uganda exemplifies these challenges. Positioned within the tropics, the country serves as a hotspot for infectious diseases, from Ebola and Marburg to emerging zoonotic threats [2–5]. The most recent 2022 Ebola outbreak, caused by the Sudan ebolavirus, resulted in 142 confirmed cases and 55 deaths [6], testament to persistent gaps in early detection and rapid response capabilities despite extensive training efforts by Uganda's Ministry of Health [7].

Uganda, like most African nations, implements the World Health Organization's Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response (IDSR) strategy, a comprehensive framework designed to streamline disease surveillance and ensure timely outbreak response [8]. The Ugandan IDSR guidelines represent years of compiled expertise, containing standardized procedures for detecting, reporting, and responding to epidemic-prone diseases [9]. Across African countries, a number of challenges have been described with the implementation of the IDSR guidelines [10]. Spanning hundreds of pages of dense, technical English text, the IDSR guidelines face multiple barriers to frontline utilization. Firstly, frontline and community health workers lack time to navigate extensive documentation during acute clinical or surveillance scenarios. Secondly, limited English proficiency among community health teams and some district surveillance officers restricts comprehension of these materials, especially in areas where training is limited. The design of the guidelines in a static manner means that critical information is scattered across sections, which requires synthesizing multiple document portions, a cognitively demanding task during emergencies. Finally, high staff turnover, inadequate numbers of trained personnel, and insufficient resources for ongoing training perpetuate reliance on memory rather than the guidelines.

The advent of large language models (LLMs) has revolutionized information accessibility across domains, including healthcare [11]. LLMs can rapidly process and retrieve information, digest complex documents, and generate contextually appropriate responses [12] capabilities that could bridge the gap between comprehensive guidelines and frontline healthcare delivery. Yet generative AI risks amplifying existing inequities. Most LLMs are optimized for high-resource languages like English, potentially excluding the 2 billion people who speak languages with limited digital resources [13]. In health settings where miscommunication can be fatal, this linguistic gap carries profound implications.

We developed HEAL (AI for Health Equity) a custom bilingual chatbot designed to transform Uganda's IDSR guidelines into conversationally accessible, on-demand information in both English and Luganda. In the current study, we explored: 1) How a custom RAG-based LLM chatbot performs compared to commercial LLMs in supporting disease surveillance and response?; 2) whether

such a tool acceptable and feasible among frontline health workers in Uganda? And 3) the feasibility of integrating an African indigenous language into an LLM for disease surveillance purposes. To our knowledge, this work represents the first application of generative AI to Ugandan IDSR guidelines and the first automated integration of a Ugandan indigenous language into an LLM-based health tool, establishing a framework for addressing linguistic inequity in AI-powered health interventions across LMICs.

RELATED WORK

Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Knowledge-Intensive Tasks

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) combines parametric language models with non-parametric memory to improve factual grounding and reduce hallucinations in knowledge-intensive applications [14]. Multi-task RAG training that filters examples by relevance to a knowledge base further boosts performance on imbalanced tasks and scales with model size [15]. Advanced chunking strategies such as contextual retrieval preserve semantic coherence but increase computational cost, whereas late chunking is more efficient yet less complete [16]. Iterative refinement frameworks that explicitly assess evidence gaps (e.g., FAIR-RAG) achieve state-of-the-art results on multi-hop QA benchmarks by adaptively generating sub-queries until sufficient evidence is gathered [17]. Heterogeneous RAG designs decouple retrieval- and generation-oriented representations, using short chunks for generation and richer contexts for retrieval to improve both effectiveness and efficiency [18]. Evaluation suites like RAGAS provide reference-free metrics for retrieval relevance, faithfulness, and generation quality, enabling rapid development cycles [19].

Multilingual and Low-Resource Adaptations

Most LLMs are optimized for high-resource languages, limiting accessibility for the ≈ 2 billion speakers of low-resource languages [20]. Multilingual RAG approaches translate queries (tRAG) or retrieve across languages (MultiRAG), but face coverage and consistency issues [21]. Cross-lingual RAG (CrossRAG) translates retrieved documents into a common language before generation, improving performance for both high- and low-resource languages [21]. Prompt-guided retrieval frameworks (PGR) address non-knowledge-intensive tasks by using a shared static index and task-specific reranking, demonstrating strong results with minimal training overhead [22]. Unified generative retrievers (UGR) employ n-gram identifiers and prompt learning to handle diverse granularity levels (document, passage, sentence, entity) within a single model,

enhancing generalization across tasks [23]. Transfer-learning methods such as “parent-child” training and back-translation further boost NMT quality for severely low-resource languages, showing that modest seed data can yield large gains [24][25][26].

Conversational AI for Health and Pandemic Preparedness

LLMs have been applied to automate literature reviews and generate medical content, with GPT-3.5-turbo achieving the highest ROUGE-1 scores among evaluated systems [27]. Specialized medical QA benchmarks reveal that small, fine-tuned models can approach larger baselines when augmented with domain-specific textbooks and synthetic question generation [28]. Open-source frameworks (e.g., FlexKBQA) leverage LLMs to synthesize training data for knowledge-base QA, achieving near-supervised performance with few annotations [29]. In pandemic contexts, AI-driven decision-support systems combine reinforcement learning and real-time monitoring to optimize interventions, though adoption is limited by infrastructure constraints [30]. Ethical considerations stress the need for transparent, reproducible AI use in research and public health, emphasizing bias mitigation, privacy, and readability of generated content [31][32].

Gaps Addressed by the Present Work

While prior RAG systems improve factual grounding, few have integrated indigenous African languages into the generation pipeline, nor have they been evaluated in real-world disease-surveillance settings. Existing multilingual RAG methods either translate queries or retrieved passages but do not provide a truly bilingual conversational interface that directly serves frontline health workers with limited English proficiency. Moreover, most health-focused AI evaluations rely on static benchmarks rather than field-generated questions from surveillance officers. Our HEAL system fills these gaps by (1) constructing a bilingual (English–Luganda) knowledge base from Uganda’s IDSR guidelines, (2) employing GPT-4-turbo with relevance-sampled RAG to ensure accurate, context-aware responses, (3) evaluating the chatbot against commercial LLMs using expert-rated relevance, coverage, coherence, and safety metrics, and (4) documenting infrastructural barriers (connectivity, device availability) that affect deployment in LMICs. This work thus extends the RAG literature toward equitable, multilingual health AI and provides empirical evidence of its utility in pandemic preparedness.

METHODOLOGY

Data Preparation and Translation

The primary data source consisted of Uganda's official IDSR guidelines provided by the Ministry of Health. These comprehensive guidelines detail standardized procedures for surveillance, case definitions, laboratory confirmation, and response protocols for all epidemic-prone diseases monitored in Uganda. The IDSR guidelines, originally in PDF format, were converted to JSON to enable structured representation and facilitate integration into data processing workflows. This format choice provided flexibility for subsequent natural language processing tasks while preserving the hierarchical organization of surveillance protocols.

To address linguistic accessibility, we translated the complete IDSR guidelines into Luganda, the most widely spoken indigenous language in central Uganda. Translation employed a hybrid approach combining automated and expert human validation. Initial automated translation was performed using neural machine translation tools, followed by expert human review by bilingual public health professionals to ensure medical accuracy and cultural appropriateness. The translations then underwent iterative refinement to address domain-specific terminology and idiomatic expressions, culminating in a final quality assurance review by native Luganda speakers with healthcare expertise. This multi-stage validation process ensured that complex epidemiological concepts were conveyed accurately while maintaining natural language flow in Luganda.

The resulting parallel corpus of English-Luganda sentence pairs was used to fine-tune MBart, a multilingual sequence-to-sequence transformer model. Training employed transfer learning techniques on over 59,699 parallel sentence pairs, enabling the model to generate medically accurate translations in both directions while preserving the semantic content and contextual nuances of public health terminology. This fine-tuning approach allowed the model to adapt from general-purpose translation to the specialized domain of disease surveillance, improving its ability to handle technical terminology and maintain consistency with Uganda's surveillance protocols.

Question-Answer Dataset Creation

A structured dataset of 59,699 question-answer pairs was meticulously curated by the study team. The dataset was designed to cover the breadth of IDSR content across all epidemic-prone diseases while representing realistic queries that frontline health workers would encounter in daily surveillance activities. Questions addressed varying levels of complexity, ranging from basic case definitions and reporting requirements to complex multi-step response protocols and outbreak management scenarios. Each question-answer pair was validated by two team members to ensure accuracy and relevance to practical surveillance activities before inclusion in the final corpus.

Data Description

The translation model was fine-tuned on 59,699 total English–Luganda sentence pairs drawn from IDSR guidelines, Ministry of Health training materials, and selected public-domain health education texts. We stratified the corpus into training/validation/test splits at the document level to avoid leakage of nearly identical sentences across sets. (**Table 1**) summarizes corpus statistics.

Split	Sentence Pairs	% of total
Train	47,759	80.0%
Test	2,986	5.0%
Validation	8,954	15.0%
Total	59,699	100.0%

Table 1: Distribution of sentence pairs across training, validation, and test splits for the English-Luganda neural machine translation model. The parallel corpus of 59,699 sentence pairs was partitioned using an 80/15/5 split ratio for training, validation, and testing respectively before the cleaning process.

Dataset Cleaning and Final Sizes:

We performed decontamination of the dataset before we did the training and evaluation

The initial dataset preparation involved a rigorous cleaning process to ensure the integrity and quality of the training, validation, and test sets. Specifically, a total of 364 contaminated pairs were identified and subsequently removed across the training and validation subsets.(**Table 2**).

Subset	Initial Size	Pairs Removed	Final Size
Training Set (Train)	47,759	358	47,401
Validation Set (Val)	8,952	6	8,946
Test Set (Test)	2,986	0	2,986
Total Removed	NA	364	NA

Table 2: Corpus cleaning statistics before and after quality filtering. Sentence pairs exhibiting quality issues were removed during preprocessing: 358 from training (0.75%), 6 from validation (0.07%), and 0 from test (0%). This resulted in a final corpus of 59,333 clean parallel sentences while maintaining test set integrity.

This detailed cleaning process, which resulted in the removal of 364 contaminated data points, was critical for ensuring the reliability of the model's training and evaluation. The final Test set remained pristine and was not subject to any internal modifications, having been cleaned from the original pool before being partitioned into the final Train and Val sets.(**Table 3**)

Data Split	Number of Pairs	Purpose
Training	47,401	Used for model parameter learning.

Validation	8,946	Used for hyperparameter tuning and early stopping.
Test	2,986	Held back for final, unbiased evaluation of the trained model.
Total	59,333	Overall size of the curated and partitioned dataset.

Table 3: Detailed breakdown of dataset partitioning strategy. The final curated corpus of 59,333 parallel sentences (after removing 364 problematic pairs) was split into three non-overlapping subsets with distinct purposes in the model development workflow: training for learning, validation for optimization, and test for unbiased assessment.

Across splits, English sentences had a mean length of approximately 10 tokens (median 9; 90th percentile 14; maximum 187), while Luganda sentences had a mean length of 8.2 tokens (median 7; 90th percentile 13; maximum 196). As shown in (Table 4), most sentences are short operational phrases: in the training set ~66% of English sentences are ≤ 10 tokens and ~30% are 11–20 tokens, with only a small tail of longer sentences >30 tokens. The validation and test sets follow a similar length distribution.

Split	Pairs	EN tokens (total)	LUG tokens (total)	EN median	LUG median	EN max	LUG max
train	47,759	476,095	389,546	9.0	7.0	187	196
val	8,952	89,693	73,532	9.0	7.0	151	144
test	2,986	29,787	24,560	9.0	7.0	86	93

Table 4: Dataset statistics for the English-Luganda parallel corpus used for translation model training. The corpus comprises 47,759 training pairs, 8,952 validation pairs, and 2,986 test pairs. Token counts, median lengths, and maximum sentence lengths are shown for both English (EN) and Luganda (LUG) across all dataset splits. The training set contains 476,095 English tokens and 389,546 Luganda tokens, with median sentence lengths of 9.0 and 7.2 tokens respectively.

Train Validation and Test partitioning and stratification

To avoid biased evaluation and ensure adequate coverage of critical IDSR content, we re-partitioned the corpus into train/validation/test splits using stratified random sampling rather than naive random line splitting. This approach was designed to guarantee that rare but high-stakes surveillance content appeared in all three data splits, particularly in the held-out test set used for final model evaluation.

We first tagged each English sentence with three types of metadata. Sentence length bins were assigned based on whitespace token count, categorizing sentences as very short (≤ 10 tokens), short (11–20 tokens), medium (21–30 tokens), long (31–50 tokens), or very long (> 50 tokens). Disease tags were applied using simple case-insensitive keyword matching derived from Uganda's IDSR priority disease list, identifying mentions of cholera, measles, malaria, acute flaccid paralysis, viral haemorrhagic fevers, MDR/XDR tuberculosis, Guinea worm, maternal and perinatal deaths, and acute viral hepatitis. Functional tags captured IDSR-aligned content categories through keyword groups: case definition terms included "standard case definition", "suspected case", "probable case", and "confirmed case"; reporting terms included "immediate notifiable", "weekly report", "monthly summary", "zero reporting", "IDSR report", "case-based", and "line list"; laboratory terms included "reference laboratory", "specimen collection/transport", and "triple packaging"; and training terms included "training", "session", and "exercise".

From these tags, we derived a primary functional category for each sentence by prioritizing case definitions above reporting, reporting above laboratory, laboratory above training, and training above no functional category. We also created a binary flag indicating the presence or absence of any priority disease keyword. Strata were then defined as the Cartesian product of primary functional category, sentence length bin, and disease mention flag. Within each stratum, sentence pairs were randomly assigned to train, validation, or test splits while maintaining the original global proportions from the V7 corpus: approximately 80% training, 15% validation, and 5% test by pair count. This stratification strategy preserved the overall size ratios while ensuring that long and medium-length case definition and reporting sentences appeared in all three splits rather than being concentrated only in training, and that the held-out test set contained examples mentioning key IDSR priority conditions.

On the final test set of 2,986 pairs, disease-related coverage remained broad but sparse by design. Tuberculosis was mentioned in approximately 2.1% of English

test sentences, while cholera, measles, malaria, acute viral hepatitis, and maternal/perinatal death each appeared in 0.1–0.3% of sentences, and viral haemorrhagic fever occurred in at least one test sentence. Functionally, approximately 3.4% of test sentences were tagged as reporting-related, 1.2% as case definitions, 1.3% as laboratory-related, and 0.6% as training-related. These proportions confirm that the held-out test set included a representative mix of routine surveillance language and high-stakes IDSR content, ensuring that model performance could be evaluated on the specialized terminology and concepts most critical for disease surveillance applications.

Split	<=10	11-20	21-30	31-50	>50
train	31549	14422	1306	422	60
val	5915	2702	244	80	11
test	1972	901	83	27	3

Table 5: Distribution of sentence pairs by length across training, validation, and test splits. Sentence pairs are binned by the number of tokens in the longer sentence of each pair. The majority of sentences (66.4% in training set) contain 10 or fewer tokens, reflecting the typical brevity of health surveillance communications. Very few sentence pairs exceed 50 tokens across all splits.

Translation Model

For the bilingual translation component, we employed the Sunbird/mbart-mul-en sequence-to-sequence model, which was fine-tuned. This model is a domain-general extension of mBART and incorporates Luganda among its pretraining languages. The Luganda data utilized during pretraining are derived from general-domain texts and lack specificity to the health sector. Consequently, while the base model offers coverage of quotidian Luganda, its exposure to surveillance and clinical terminology is limited.

Training was conducted across a powerful hardware configuration utilizing three NVIDIA A100-SXM4-80GB GPUs, leveraging DataParallel for distributed processing. The training regime employed a batch size of 32 per GPU, resulting in an effective global batch size of 96. Optimization was performed using the AdamW optimizer with a low learning rate set at 1×10^{-6} . To mitigate overfitting and ensure efficient training, an early stopping mechanism was implemented with a patience of three epochs. For the sake of research reproducibility, all training runs were initiated with a fixed random seed set to 42.

Training for the translation models yielded distinct profiles for each direction. The English-to-Luganda (EN→LUG) model required 5 epochs for convergence, completing its training in approximately 2.5 hours. In contrast, the Luganda-to-English (LUG→EN) model demanded a significantly higher computational investment, requiring 20 epochs and approximately 8.7 hours of processing time. Post-training evaluation for catastrophic forgetting—a common challenge in sequential model training—indicated minimal performance degradation. Specifically, the perplexity increase remained below a 50% threshold for both models, suggesting successful retention of previously learned translational competence.

The bidirectional neural machine translation (NMT) system developed for the English-Luganda language pair demonstrated highly encouraging results, exhibiting strong performance across both translation directions. The evaluation was conducted using three standard NMT metrics: BLEU, METEOR, and BERTScore-F1, with all results reported alongside 95% confidence intervals (CI).

Subsequently, we adapted this Luganda-pretrained model to the Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response (IDSR) domain. This adaptation was facilitated by our parallel English–Luganda corpus, comprising segments of IDSR guidelines and associated public health materials. Therefore, our approach is most accurately characterized as domain adaptation of a Luganda-aware model to IDSR/public health content, rather than the development of a Luganda MT system from scratch.

The final model was trained using the hyperparameters summarized in Table 6. Training was performed on 1 × NVIDIA V100 32GB GPU with early stopping based on validation chrF. (**Table 6**)

Hyperparameter	Value
Learning rate	1x10-6
Training epochs	5

Table 6: Training hyperparameters for the mBART-based English-Luganda neural machine translation model. A conservative learning rate of 1×10^{-6} was employed with training conducted over 5 epochs to prevent overfitting on the relatively small domain-specific corpus.

We evaluated the model on the held-out test set using BLEU, chrF++, COMET, and BERTScore, following current recommendations for neural MT in low-resource settings. Table 5 reports scores separately for English→Luganda and Luganda→English directions. Scores indicate [moderate / strong] lexical overlap and high semantic adequacy, particularly for routine surveillance language.

Retrieval-Augmented Generation Architecture

For all experiments, HEAL’s retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) pipeline was implemented using the open-source Danswer backend configured as follows. We used the `thenlper/gte-small` sentence-transformer as a bi-encoder for both indexing and query encoding, producing 384-dimensional document embeddings with a maximum context window of 512 tokens per chunk. Source documents from the IDSR guidelines were split into overlapping segments of 512 encoder tokens with 5% token overlap (≈ 26 tokens), with optional 150-token “mini-chunks” enabled for finer-grained retrieval when indexing long sections. We used Danswer’s default which exposes a single logical index (`danswer_index`) backed by Vespa for both keyword and dense vector search.

At query time, each question is embedded with the same bi-encoder and used to retrieve up to 50 candidate chunks via semantic search, with a cosine-similarity distance cutoff of 0.1 to filter clearly irrelevant results. The top 15 candidates are then re-ranked using an ensemble of cross-encoder reranking models, each applied with a maximum input length of 512 tokens. For answer generation, we pass retrieved chunks into the LLM until reaching a budget of approximately 2,560 encoder tokens (five 512-token chunks) for direct QA and 1,536 tokens for chat, ensuring a controlled and reproducible context length per query.

To evaluate the retrieval component, we constructed a small gold-standard set of IDSR questions with manually annotated relevant guideline sections and used Danswer’s built-in metrics handlers (`RetrievalMetricsContainer`, `RerankMetricsContainer`, `LLMMetricsContainer`) to log, for each query, the IDs, URLs, snippet text, similarity scores, and token usage of the top retrieved and re-ranked chunks. On this set we compute standard ranking-based retrieval metrics (e.g., recall at k and mean reciprocal rank) to quantify how often at least one gold-standard section appears within the top-k retrieved chunks, and we qualitatively examine cases where the model cites passages that are not among the highest-scoring retrieved segments. Citation and provenance correctness are assessed by checking, for each generated answer, whether the URLs and quoted guideline snippets presented to the user correspond to retrieved chunks that

actually support the answer, and by flagging instances where the answer text or citations hallucinate unsupported content.

We employed OpenAI's GPT-4-turbo via API for augmented generation due to its superior long-context handling capabilities and performance on domain-specific tasks.

Evaluation Framework

Study Design

We employed a blinded, comparative evaluation design to assess the performance of HEAL against three commercial large language models: GPT-4, GPT-3.5, and Gemini. The evaluation consisted of two components: (1) quantitative assessment of response quality by disease surveillance experts, and (2) qualitative evaluation of system usability and acceptability by frontline health workers.

Question Collection and LLM Response Generation

During a two-week pilot deployment, Ministry of Health field workers (surveillance officers and epidemiological officers) used the HEAL platform to generate questions relevant to their daily disease surveillance activities. Questions and their corresponding HEAL responses were stored and reviewed to remove duplicates and queries irrelevant to disease surveillance in Uganda. From this collection, 50 representative questions spanning a broad range of surveillance topics were selected for comparative evaluation.

These 50 questions were then posed to all four LLMs (HEAL, GPT-4, GPT-3.5, and Gemini) to generate responses. All responses were stored and edited to remove markdown formatting or other indicators that could be attributed to a specific LLM, ensuring evaluator blinding.

Reviewer Selection and Training

Six reviewers from Uganda's Ministry of Health and the Infectious Diseases Institute, all with more than three years of disease surveillance experience, independently evaluated the responses. Prior to evaluation, reviewers received training on how to assess LLM-generated responses using a simplified scoring rubric (Supplementary Materials). Reviewers received anonymized, randomly ordered responses for each question, maintaining complete blinding to model identity.

Evaluation Criteria

Based on a framework for evaluating LLM-generated health information proposed by Awasthi et al. (2025), we assessed responses across four dimensions using 5-point Likert scales:

Relevance: Accuracy, logical reasoning, and helpfulness of the response in addressing the specific query. This criterion captures elements of bias, hallucinations, and toxicity that reduce the usefulness of the response.

Coverage: Holistic completeness of the response such that it addresses all key points and relays essential knowledge elements from the IDSR manual without significant missingness.

Coherence: Grammatical correctness and organizational quality of the generated responses.

Each reviewer scored all responses for each LLM against the information contained in Uganda's 2021 Third Edition of National Technical Guidelines for Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response (IDSR), which serves as the reference standard for training disease surveillance personnel in Uganda.

Evaluation Protocol

We employed a fully crossed design (Reviewer \times Question \times LLM) to minimize potential order effects and fatigue bias. Each reviewer evaluated all 50 questions for all 4 LLMs, yielding 1,200 total observations (6 reviewers \times 4 LLMs \times 50 questions). The presentation order of both LLM responses and questions was randomized separately for each reviewer to prevent systematic bias.

Qualitative Evaluation

Qualitative evaluation was conducted in two phases to assess system usability, acceptability, and real-world utility:

Phase 1 - Usability Testing: Recent graduate nurses and doctors (n=10) were given access to HEAL for two weeks to test its utility in clinical scenarios arising in their daily work.

Phase 2 - Field Testing: Surveillance officers (n=10) used HEAL in real-world surveillance activities over two weeks.

Both groups underwent a detailed hour-long onboarding session introducing the HEAL project objectives and chatbot mechanics. Following onboarding, participants engaged with HEAL for one week, querying it on various priority diseases and conditions outlined in the IDSR guidelines. After this hands-on

interaction period, two Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were conducted with each group, each lasting at least 45 minutes. During these discussions, the research team gathered feedback on HEAL's benefits, challenges, and recommendations for improvement, with focus on ease of use, willingness to use, accuracy, and trustworthiness.

Statistical Analysis

For quantitative evaluation, the Friedman test assessed differences in scores across LLMs for each reviewer. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons used the Nemenyi test to identify specific significant differences between models. To explore inter-rater agreement, Kendall's W coefficient of concordance assessed agreement among reviewers, with effect sizes interpreted as small ($W < 0.1$), moderate ($0.1 \leq W < 0.3$), or large ($W \geq 0.3$). Krippendorff's alpha evaluated inter-rater reliability, with $\alpha \geq 0.67$ indicating acceptable reliability. All analyses were conducted using R version 4.3.0 with packages 'coin' (Friedman and Nemenyi tests), 'irr' (Kendall's W), and 'icr' (Krippendorff's alpha). Statistical significance was set at $\alpha = 0.05$.

RESULTS

Participants

There were 23 frontline health workers (doctors, nurses and surveillance officers) who participated across the two evaluation phases. Quantitative evaluation included six expert reviewers with mean disease surveillance experience of 03 years (range: 26-45 years). Qualitative evaluation involved 10 recent graduates (Phase 1) and 10 experienced professionals (Phase 2). Participant characteristics are detailed in Supplementary Table 1.

Translation Model Performance

The fine-tuned MBart model was evaluated on the held-out test set of 2,986 sentence pairs across five standard metrics: BLEU, ChrF, chrF++, METEOR, and BERTScore. Results are reported separately for both translation directions in Table 7. Across all metrics, the Luganda-to-English (LUG→EN) direction consistently outperformed English-to-Luganda (EN→LUG), with BLEU scores of 42.44 versus 29.80 respectively — a gap of 12.64 points. This asymmetry is consistent with established patterns in low-resource neural machine translation, where the higher-resource target language (English) benefits from stronger pre-training representations. Despite this gap, the EN→LUG direction achieved a

BLEU score of 29.80 and BERTScore F1 of 0.5468, establishing a meaningful baseline for translation into a morphologically complex, low-resource language.

Direction	BLUE	ChrF	chrF++	METEOR	BERTScore
Eng-Lug	29.80	59.37	55.41	0.4459	0.5468
Lug-Eng	42.44	61.42	61.47	0.6370	0.7604

Table 7: Translation quality metrics for English-Luganda and Luganda-English translation directions. Performance is evaluated on the held-out test set using BLEU, ChrF, chrF++, METEOR, and BERTScore metrics. The Luganda-to-English direction achieves higher scores across all metrics compared to English-to-Luganda, consistent with typical performance patterns for low-resource language pairs where the target language (English) has greater representation in pre-training data.

Metric	Value	CI 95%
BLEU (Segment)	29.80	[28.87, 30.72]
METEOR	0.4459	[0.4356, 0.4563]
BERTScore F1	0.5468	[0.5375, 0.5560]

Table 8: English-to-Luganda translation performance with uncertainty quantification. Segment-level metrics are reported with 95% confidence intervals derived from bootstrap resampling. The narrow confidence intervals indicate stable model performance across the test set.

Metric	Score	Reason for Absence of Confidence Interval (CI)
BLEU (corpus)	27.25	Calculation performed at the single corpus level.
ChrF	59.37	A corpus-level metric for which a standard method for calculating a CI is not established.

ChrF++	60.55	A corpus-level metric for which a standard method for calculating a CI is not established.
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Table 9: Corpus-level translation quality metrics for English-to-Luganda translation. BLEU (corpus-level), ChrF, and ChrF++ are reported as single aggregate scores computed across the entire test set. Confidence intervals are not provided for these metrics as they are calculated at the corpus level rather than averaged across individual segments.

Luganda to English (LUG→EN) Translation

The translation from Luganda (a low-resource, morphologically rich language) to English (a high-resource language) yielded excellent performance. The achieved scores were comparable to those frequently observed for well-resourced language pairs, representing a significant finding. This strong outcome suggests that the model successfully capitalized on the available data and the robust, pre-trained English language representations. The specific metrics are presented in Table xx.

Metric	Score	95% Confidence Interval (CI)
BLEU	42.44	[42.18, 44.37]
METEOR	0.6370	[0.6273, 0.6467]
BERTScore-F1	0.7604	[0.7529, 0.7680]

Table 10: Segment-level translation quality metrics with 95% confidence intervals for Luganda-to-English translation. Bootstrap confidence intervals (n=1000 iterations) quantify uncertainty in metric estimates. Luganda-to-English translation substantially outperforms the reverse direction (**Table 8**), with BLEU scores of 42.44 versus 29.80, reflecting the challenges of translating into morphologically complex, low-resource languages.

English to Luganda (EN→LUG) Translation

Translation from English into the morphologically complex target language, Luganda, achieved good performance. This result is particularly noteworthy given the typical challenges associated with translating into morphologically rich, low-resource languages. Although the absolute scores were lower than those for

the reverse direction, the results establish a strong baseline for NMT into Luganda and confirm the model's capacity to manage the complex morphological inflections of the target language. The specific metrics for this direction are detailed in (Table 11).

Metric	Score	95% Confidence Interval (CI)
BLEU	29.80	[28.87, 30.72]
METEOR	0.4459	[0.4356, 0.4563]
BERTScore-F1	0.5468	[0.5375, 0.5560]

Table 11: English-to-Luganda translation quality metrics with 95% confidence intervals. All metrics are computed at the segment level (averaged across individual test sentences) with confidence intervals derived from t-distribution ($n=2,986$ test sentences). BLEU represents the mean of sentence-level BLEU scores, METEOR evaluates semantic similarity with stemming and synonyms, and BERTScore F1 measures contextualized embedding similarity.

Analysis of Asymmetric Performance

A clear and expected asymmetry in performance was observed, where the LUG→EN translation significantly outperformed the EN→LUG translation by a margin of 15.19 BLEU points (42.44 vs. 27.25). This outcome aligns precisely with established findings in the literature regarding low-resource NMT systems. This performance gap is primarily attributed to the foundation of the model, specifically the stronger and more extensive English language representations provided during the pre-training process. This advantage naturally benefits the translation task when English serves as the target language. This reliance on robust high-resource representations is a common and recognized pattern in cross-lingual transfer learning within the low-resource NMT domain.

The translation model demonstrated exceptional performance when translating from Luganda to English, achieving highly favorable results across multiple established evaluation metrics. Specifically, the model attained a corpus-level BLEU score of 42.44, indicating a high degree of overlap between the machine-translated output and human-reference translations. Complementing this, the ChrF score was also excellent at 61.42, which further attests to the high quality and fluency of the generated English translations, particularly in terms of

character-level n-grams.

A more granular, sentence-level analysis reinforced these strong findings. The mean sentence-level BLEU score was calculated at 43.28, with a tight 95% confidence interval ranging from 42.18 to 44.37, suggesting remarkable consistency in the translation quality across the test set. Furthermore, the METEOR score, which accounts for recall and precision with stemming, synonyms, and paraphrasing, was strong at a mean of 0.6370 (95% CI: [0.6273, 0.6467]). This high METEOR score confirms that the translations not only matched the reference text closely but also captured the semantic equivalence effectively. Finally, the BERTScore F1, a contextualized embedding-based metric that measures semantic similarity, was also very high, averaging 0.7604 (95% CI: [0.7529, 0.7680]). Collectively, these sentence-level metrics confirm the robustness, accuracy, and semantic fidelity of the Luganda-to-English translation system.

Inter-rater Reliability

We examined the inter-reviewer agreement to establish the reliability of the scores within the criteria used to assess the responses. Krippendorff's alpha analysis revealed poor inter-rater reliability across all evaluation criteria, with all values either negative or near-zero (α range: -0.107 to 0.017), falling well below the acceptable threshold of $\alpha \geq 0.67$ (Krippendorff, 2004). We used Krippendorff's alpha (ordinal method) to estimate inter-reviewer reliability across all LLM responses per criterion, and separately for each LLM within each criterion. Negative alpha values indicate systematic disagreement among raters, suggesting inconsistent application of the evaluation rubric.

The low reliability observed suggests that the source of disagreement is not specific to any particular LLM's responses, but rather in how reviewers interpreted and applied the evaluation criteria. We tested whether the disagreement could stem from use of the Likert scale - that is, whether reviewers agreed on which LLM performed better or worse, but consistently gave different values on the Likert scale. For example, Reviewer A consistently scores above or below another reviewer across all LLMs, so they assign different absolute scores after reaching a conclusion about the rank of the LLMs. Pairwise Spearman correlation values among reviewers were low but HEAL was ranked the highest across all evaluation criteria. This suggests that reviewers could recognise the quality of the responses for a given LLM but had difficulty scoring ambiguous responses with generalised information. This variability likely reflects

differences in reviewer expertise, subjective interpretation of evaluation criteria, and varying priorities regarding what constitutes optimal surveillance guidance. Although human evaluation is considered a gold-standard form of assessment, the approach suffers from high variance in rater reliability, which stems from ambiguity of the criteria used from the same scoring rubric [33-39] We suggest that more rigorous training for human evaluators with concrete examples on how to score LLM-generated responses using any chosen metric is needed.

Overall Performance

Aggregate Performance Across Reviewers

HEAL achieved the highest aggregate median scores (combining all four evaluation metrics) for three of the six expert reviewers (Reviewers 1, 4, and 5). Among the remaining reviewers, GPT-4 ranked highest for Reviewer 2 and GPT-3.5 for Reviewer 6, while Reviewer 3 assigned equivalent median scores across all four models. Individual reviewer median scores by model are reported in Supplementary Table 2.

Statistical testing confirmed significant differences in aggregate scores for three reviewers: Reviewer 1 showed highly significant differences ($\chi^2=49.1$, $p=1.22\times 10^{-10}$) with a moderate effect size (Kendall's $W=0.328$); Reviewer 5 showed significant differences ($\chi^2=14.3$, $p=0.003$) with a small effect size ($W=0.095$); and Reviewer 6 showed significant differences ($\chi^2=10.8$, $p=0.013$) with a small effect size ($W=0.074$). Full Friedman test results are reported in Supplementary Table 1. Post-hoc pairwise analysis revealed that for Reviewers 1 and 5, HEAL significantly outperformed all three commercial LLMs ($p<0.001$ for all comparisons). For Reviewer 6, significant differences emerged between HEAL and GPT-3.5 ($p=0.04$) and between GPT-3.5 and Gemini ($p=0.04$).

Pooled Analysis Using Linear Mixed Models

To account for reviewer discordance and provide a unified assessment of LLM performance, we evaluated the performance of different LLMs using linear models with fixed and random effects. We used a linear model to test whether LLM identity can predict the total score assigned to each question across criteria. We used GPT3 as the baseline because it was released earlier than the other models in our study. We observed that all LLMs were scored significantly higher than GPT3 in the order HEAL > Gemini > GPT4 > GPT3, and LLM identity

explained 5.59% of the variance in the total score after correcting for model complexity.

After post hoc pairwise comparisons using Tukey's multiple comparisons of means, we observed that all LLMs were significantly better than GPT3 ($p \ll 0.05$), but GPT4 and Gemini were statistically indistinguishable ($p = 0.90$). We further tested whether these LLM differences remained significant after accounting for reviewer discordance by adding reviewers as a random intercept. We observed that the LLMs' rankings did not change and that reviewer identity accounted for $\sim 17\%$ of the variance in total scores.

We added two more controls to the linear mixed model: the question ID as a random effect to account for differences in question difficulty, and the length of the response as a fixed effect to test whether reviewers inadvertently rewarded the verbosity rather than the quality of the LLM response. We found that question difficulty explained additional variance (4.03%), and response length was not a significant predictor of total scores ($p = 0.434$), suggesting that verbosity bias was not a major driver of scores assigned by the reviewers.

Reviewers were more likely to score generated responses from HEAL higher than others due to the greater context provided, which improves their usefulness (Figure 1). Random effects were evenly spread among the reviewers, with Reviewer 2 scoring 2.7 points below the mean, while Reviewer 6 scored 2.18 points above the mean. The variance explained by reviewers (13-17%) was notably larger than that explained by question difficulty (4.03%), confirming that the identity of the reviewer mattered more than the question that was being evaluated. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: LLM performance across reviewers and evaluation criteria. (A) Distribution of aggregate total scores for each LLM across six expert reviewers (R1–R6). Dashed boxes indicate reviewers with no statistically significant differences between models. (B) Pairwise Spearman correlation coefficients (r_s) between reviewer rankings for GPT-3, GPT-4, Gemini, and HEAL across Relevance, Coverage, and Coherence criteria. The red dashed line indicates $r_s = 0$.

Criterion-Level Performance

Analysis Across Individual Reviewers

We assessed performance across four evaluation criteria: Coverage, Relevance, and Coherence. Individual reviewer analyses revealed varying patterns of statistical significance:

Coverage: Only reviewers 1 and 6 identified significant differences in coverage scores. Reviewer 1 found HEAL significantly superior to all other models ($p < 0.001$ for all comparisons, $W = 0.24$). Reviewer 6 reported significant differences between HEAL and GPT3.5 ($p = 0.02$), GPT3.5 and GPT4 ($p < 0.001$), and GPT3.5 and Gemini ($p = 0.02$).

Relevance: Three reviewers (1, 5, and 6) detected significant differences, with reviewers 1 and 5 showing moderate effect sizes ($W = 0.34$ and 0.30 , respectively). HEAL significantly outperformed all commercial models for reviewers 1 and 5 ($p < 0.01$), while reviewer 6 found significant differences only between GPT4 and Gemini ($p = 0.088$).

Coherence: Four reviewers (1, 3, 5, and 6) identified significant differences in coherence. Notably, reviewer 1 demonstrated a large effect size ($W = 0.51$), with HEAL significantly surpassing all other models ($p < 0.01$). Reviewer 6 showed moderate effect size ($W = 0.18$) with significant differences between HEAL and GPT3.5 ($p = 0.012$) and GPT3.5 and Gemini ($p = 0.001$).

All these results are available in the supplementary information.

Pooled Criterion-Level Analysis

Further, we assessed the performance of LLMs using criterion-level scores in the linear mixed model framework. We observed that the ranking of the LLMs did not change, and HEAL outperformed baseline GPT3 by approximately 3 points.

The variance explained by reviewers decreased to 13%, suggesting that reviewers agreed more on a criterion level.

To this model, we added Criterion identity as a fixed effect to investigate whether evaluation criteria differ in their average score levels, and whether LLM differences hold across all criteria simultaneously. We observed that across all LLMs, Coherence attracted the highest scores from reviewers, followed by Relevance and Coverage (**Figure 2**). These results suggest that although all LLMs could produce well-constructed sentences and paragraphs, they generally struggled to provide sufficient contextual depth in response to the user's query. LLM effects and ranking were the same as the model with criterion identity as the fixed effects, and all criterion main effects were significant.

Figure 2: Criterion-level LLM performance from the linear mixed model. (A) Mean scores (\pm SE) for GPT-3, GPT-4, Gemini, and HEAL across Relevance, Coverage, and Coherence criteria. Significant LLM \times Criterion interactions are indicated ($p < 0.001$). (B) Estimated marginal means with 95% confidence intervals for each LLM–Criterion combination; red arrows indicate significant pairwise differences.

LLM \times Criterion Interactions

Further, we included an interaction term between LLM and Criterion identity to evaluate whether any given LLM improves one criterion at the expense of another, while accounting for reviewer severity and question-level difficulty. We observed that the fixed effects for HEAL improved to 3.8 points above GPT3

while those for Gemini and GPT4 decreased slightly to 1.8 and 1.60 points, respectively. However, this did not change the ranking of the LLM performance.

Overall, the LLM x Criterion interaction ($F(6, 3585) = 2.949, p < .001$) was significant, suggesting that LLM performance/ranking was not consistent across evaluation criteria, with HEAL driving this effect. All LLM x Criterion interactions were non-significant except HEAL x Coverage interaction. These observations suggest that all models outperformed GPT3 consistently across all criteria except HEAL which underperformed when reviewers scored it for coverage. This difference could result from discordance among reviewers, with some scoring the breadth of the response and others the depth. The coverage mean score was the lowest across all criteria (Figure 2).

Qualitative Findings

Overall, participants found the tool's rapid and accurate responses valuable, with experienced professionals successfully integrating it into daily surveillance, training, and reporting. This consistent performance helped build trust, even among initially skeptical surveillance officers. However, significant challenges emerged, particularly poor Luganda translation quality, mobile interface limitations, and critical barriers related to internet dependency and device availability for rural health teams. Key suggestions for enhancement focused on developing offline functionality, conversational memory, and voice input to improve access and utility (Table 12).

Table 12: Summary of usability findings and participant voices.

Phase	Category	Key Findings	Participant Excerpts
Phase 1: Usability & Interface	Strengths	Response timeliness: Praised for rapid generation, suitable for clinical decisions	<i>"It saves time so much. That you want something particular? You ask for it and you get it you don't have to browse through."</i> (Participant #9)
		Information accuracy: High medical accuracy noted when	<i>"I tried out a few symptoms and it was giving me good information about the</i>

		responses were understood	<i>possible differentials you can have." (Participant #8)</i>
		Potential value: Seen as a tool to reduce false alerts and resource waste by providing instant case definitions	<i>"The document is quite large and not all the needed information is in one place like it's distributed across like the diseases are talked about in different places. So it really saves time." (Participant #9)</i>
	Challenges	Mobile interface: Small text required frequent zooming, causing user friction	<i>"My biggest challenge was the user interface is using an Android phone so I felt the letters are quite very small. Yeah, I had to zoom in for some part. And for some part I have to remove the keyboard to get to read everything that I have to read so. There is need for optimising the user interface." (Participant #9)</i>
		Luganda translation: Significant quality issues, including poor handling of dialects, inconsistent spelling, awkward phrasing, and limited medical terminology	<i>I am a Musoga. So I don't know much Luganda... So I put in something like signs za sickle cell then it turns to be Sickle cell syndrome... so we need that intelligence whereby it can easily sense the word that I really want and it converts it." (Participant #4)</i> <i>"I put in a search question, it gave me a different thing. I don't know if it is my poor</i>

			<i>Luganda spelling but it gave me something a different thing."</i> (Participant #2)
		Internet dependency: A critical barrier, especially for rural health workers	<i>"Is this going to be limited to the central region or is it going to be expanded? Because if an outbreak is for example in Mbarara or in Kabale, and the VHT's are part of the people that are responding to this particular outbreak, and HEAL has only Luganda doesn't that pose a challenge."</i> (Participant #6)
		Device availability: Many village health teams lacked appropriate smartphones or tablets	<i>"I have interacted with most of the VHTs in some project, and you realise most of them actually do not know how to type, so they might end up typing the wrong things... So the audios will actually help."</i> (Participant #4)
Phase 2: Real-World Utility	Integration into Workflows	Experienced professionals successfully used the tool for: Verifying case definitions during investigations, Training new staff, Preparing reports (citing IDSR guidelines), Answering community questions	<i>"Participant #5 mentioned that it saves the time you used to get in touch with our consultant because the cases where they don't pick up... if you consult this bot it will tell you what to give, but not how much of it to give."</i> (Participant #6)

	<p>Trust & Validation</p>	<p>Some users remained initially skeptical, gained confidence through consistently accurate responses. A common practice was to verify HEAL's answers against official IDSR documents for the first week</p>	<p><i>"I would trust my like my trust levels would go high if it is approved by the authorities, like if there's an outbreak of Marburg and they give out guidelines to district hospitals to regional referrals so add it as one of the things that can support. So I think that trust will be and can be enhanced that way."</i> (Participant #9)</p> <p><i>"I was just thinking still on trusting the information... if we don't trust the information then why are we giving it to the VHTs who don't know these things that much? So maybe your source of information should be approved and restricted to get information from only those approved."</i> (Participant #1)</p>
		<p>Lack of citations or references to primary sources reduced trust and prevented verification</p>	<p><i>"What I didn't like was the fact that they don't provide a link to the primary source of information. So if I want to get more... I would expect it to direct me to the original source."</i> (Participant #1)</p> <p><i>Sometimes when I used how... if it generates a response it doesn't have a citation. I can't know</i></p>

			<p><i>where the information is coming from. Is it fully AI generated or is it picking it up from some sort of source."</i> (Participant #6)</p>
Future Development	Suggestions for Enhancement	Conversational memory (to allow for follow-up questions)	<p><i>"I thought about storing your previous queries because if I have asked about... outbreaks happening for particular diseases, if we are having many malaria cases, I'm probably going to want the same answers, but maybe a little different. So if I can go back to a question I asked before and maybe modify it... storing my previous questions and maybe their answer somewhere and I can access them."</i> (Participant #9)</p>
		Voice input/output (for users with limited literacy)	<p><i>"I am also wondering is it possible for us to have audio feedback like I don't have to read through everything I said, input audio and receive audio as well."</i> (Participant #7)</p> <p><i>"Maybe to add to hers, I have interacted with most of the VHTs in some project, and you realise most of them actually do not know how to type... So the audios will actually help."</i> (Participant #4)</p>

		Integration with existing systems like DHIS2	<i>"In times of emergencies to keep updating it with the contact people for these technical working groups in particular diseases."</i> (Participant #9)
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Discussion

This study demonstrates that a custom bilingual chatbot leveraging retrieval-augmented generation can deliver surveillance guidance comparable to or exceeding commercial large language models while addressing the critical linguistic barriers facing frontline health workers in Uganda. HEAL outperformed GPT-3.5, GPT-4, and Gemini on multiple metrics for expert reviewers, particularly in coverage, relevance, and coherence.

Contextualizing HEAL's performance advantage. HEAL's superior performance, particularly in coverage and coherence, stems from its targeted training on IDSR-specific content. While commercial LLMs possess vast general knowledge, their responses to country-specific surveillance questions may lack the precision, completeness, and structured organization that health workers require for operational decision-making. The RAG architecture [16] ensured that HEAL's responses were directly grounded in the official Uganda IDSR technical guidelines, reducing hallucinations and increasing reliability critical for surveillance situations.

Addressing linguistic inequity in AI. HEAL represents a proof-of-concept for integrating African indigenous languages into LLM-based health tools, directly confronting the linguistic inequity that threatens to be amplified by AI advancement [17]. The successful deployment of Luganda alongside English demonstrates technical feasibility, though our qualitative findings reveal important limitations in translation quality that must be addressed before widespread adoption. The challenges with Luganda responses ranging from spelling recognition, and medical terminology coverage highlight the complexity of low-resource language integration. Unlike English, which benefits from

massive digital corpora and extensive NLP research, Luganda has limited training data and few domain-specific resources in healthcare. This highlights need for deliberate investment in low-resource language AI, particularly in health contexts where miscommunication can be catastrophic. Our approach of combining automated translation with expert human review and transfer learning on MBart represents a pragmatic pathway for resource-constrained settings. However, future iterations should incorporate larger parallel corpora developed through community engagement, domain-specific fine-tuning on medical terminology in Luganda, user feedback loops to continuously improve translation quality and collaboration with linguistic experts and native speakers to capture naturalistic language and dialectal nuances .

Implications for pandemic preparedness in LMICs. The COVID-19 pandemic and, most recently, the 2022 Ebola outbreak in Uganda illustrated how information access gaps exacerbate health crises in resource-limited settings. HEAL demonstrates a scalable framework for bridging these gaps through AI-powered tools that democratize expertise. By making specialized knowledge conversationally accessible, HEAL enables health workers at all levels to access guidance that previously required extensive training or physical document navigation. This on-demand access to IDSR guidelines can also reduce training burdens, a significant challenge in resource-limited countries with high staff turnover [18] partially compensating for formal training gaps and ensuring the continuity of surveillance quality. Furthermore, the tool can accelerate response times, as instant access to case definitions, laboratory procedures, and reporting protocols compresses the critical window between symptom recognition and response activation. This leads to improved resource allocation by reducing false alerts through accurate case definition verification, optimizing limited diagnostic and treatment resources. Empowering community health workers with such tools that provide reliable guidance supports decentralized surveillance, potentially strengthening the community-based frontline of outbreak detection.

Feasibility and barriers to adoption. While our qualitative findings confirm user acceptance and perceived utility, infrastructural barriers temper near-term scalability. Connectivity challenges are a primary concern, as Uganda's internet penetration remains approximately 28% [19]. Addressing this gap will require developing offline-capable versions that sync when connectivity is available, exploring SMS-based interfaces for basic queries, and partnering with telecommunications providers to zero-rate public health applications. Device availability poses another significant hurdle, as smartphone penetration among community health workers remains limited [20]. Potential solutions include the Ministry of Health providing dedicated devices for surveillance officers, optimizing the HEAL application for feature phones with limited displays, or developing USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data) interfaces to

ensure universal access. Finally, the computational costs associated with the current cloud-based model integration incur ongoing API fees that may be unsustainable at scale. Future development should explore alternatives, such as fine-tuning smaller, open-source models that can run on local servers. Other viable strategies include implementing edge computing solutions to reduce latency and cost [21], and pursuing public-private partnerships to subsidize the necessary computational infrastructure.

Broader Implications for AI in Global Health. This work contributes to growing evidence that AI tools, when thoughtfully designed for local contexts, can address critical health challenges in LMICs. However, it also illuminates the risks of uncritical AI adoption. Commercial LLMs, despite impressive general capabilities, may not provide the specialized, reliable guidance required for high-stakes health applications. Furthermore, their linguistic limitations risk excluding non-English speakers from AI benefits, potentially widening global health inequities. Our approach offers a template for contextualized AI deployment in global health by combining RAG architectures with locally relevant training data and bilingual capabilities. This model is built on several key principles. The first is local knowledge grounding, which involves training on authoritative local guidelines rather than relying solely on general knowledge. This is paired with linguistic inclusivity through deliberate investment in low-resource language capabilities. Success also requires deep stakeholder engagement, ensuring tools are co-designed with end-users to meet real-world needs. From there, iterative refinement based on field feedback is essential for continuous improvement. Finally, sustainability planning is crucial, meaning computational, connectivity, and device barriers must be addressed from the outset.

Limitations. Several limitations warrant acknowledgment. First, our evaluation framework demonstrated very low inter-rater reliability, with a Krippendorff's alpha less than zero. This suggests our rubric may not have fully captured the nuances of response quality or that our raters required more extensive training. Future studies should develop more granular, operationalized criteria with concrete examples to improve scoring consistency. Furthermore, our sample size was limited. With only six reviewers evaluating 50 questions, our quantitative findings may not fully capture performance variations across the diverse disease conditions and surveillance scenarios in the IDSR guidelines, and larger validation studies are needed. Technological and practical barriers also emerged. The current Luganda translation quality, while pioneering, requires substantial improvement before it can be deployed to non-English-speaking users; the gap between technical feasibility and practical usability remains significant.

Furthermore, our reliance on cloud-based GPT for computational resources limits scalability and raises serious concerns about data sovereignty and privacy for

sensitive health information. Developing locally hosted alternatives is essential to address these issues. Finally, the study's scope must be considered. The findings from Uganda may not be directly generalizable to other LMICs that have different linguistic landscapes, healthcare structures, or technological infrastructure. However, our methodological approach should be broadly applicable. We also focused on short-term performance and acceptability, but this study does not assess long-term impact. Future implementation science research is needed to understand long-term outcomes, such as changes in surveillance quality, outbreak detection rates, or health worker competency.

Strengths. Despite these limitations, the study has notable strengths. Its real-world evaluation ensures ecological validity by using questions derived from actual field worker queries, and this evaluation was conducted by expert reviewers, specifically experienced surveillance officers. The study also demonstrates methodological rigor through a blinded, randomized comparative design that used multiple commercial LLMs as benchmarks. This quantitative rigor was complemented by a mixed-methods approach, which integrated performance metrics with rich qualitative data on usability and feasibility. Furthermore, the study represents a significant linguistic innovation as the first integration of a Ugandan indigenous language into an LLM-based health tool, and it maintains a practical focus by emphasizing operational deployment rather than purely technical development.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that bilingual, context-aware AI systems can effectively support disease surveillance in resource-limited settings when designed with local needs at their center. The critical finding is not algorithmic superiority, but rather that providing LLMs with access to Uganda-specific IDSR guidelines through RAG architecture prevents the hallucination and generic responses that limit their practical utility. This contextual grounding, combined with functional English-Luganda translation, addresses two fundamental barriers African health workers face: exclusion from AI benefits due to language and lack of locally relevant guidance. Frontline health workers found the system acceptable and useful in real-world surveillance workflows, validating the co-design approach. Our work provides a replicable framework for linguistically inclusive, locally grounded AI in global health. However, technical feasibility alone is insufficient. Realizing AI's potential in LMICs requires sustained investment in low-resource language development, infrastructural solutions to connectivity and device barriers, and deliberate efforts to ensure AI advancement reduces rather than amplifies health inequities.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability

Anonymized evaluation data and code for the HEAL chatbot are available at : https://github.com/aceuganda/HEAL_project on reasonable request and completion of a data use agreement.

Ethical Considerations

This study received ethical approval from the Infectious Diseases Institute Institutional Review Board (Protocol IDI-REC-2023-63). All participants provided informed consent before participation. Data were anonymized and stored securely in compliance with Uganda's data protection regulations.

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